

Performance Evaluation of a Digital Platform for Rural Tourism Management in Puno “Puno Virtual”

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July , 2024

Abstract

In this study, a digital platform specifically designed for the management of rural tourism in Puno, Peru was developed. This platform, powered by modern technologies such as CodeIgniter for backend development and MySQL for database management, is a comprehensive solution that significantly improves the visibility and accessibility of rural tourism destinations. In addition, the platform incorporates interactive maps from Google Maps, providing an enriched and detailed user experience. To evaluate the quality and efficiency of the platform, Lighthouse was used, focusing on key areas such as performance, accessibility, best practices, SEO and Progressive Web App (PWA) features. This work highlights the importance and positive impact of digital technologies in the promotion and management of rural tourism, providing an effective tool to improve the user experience and foster the economic development of rural communities in Puno.

Key words: Rural tourism, destination management, digital platform, Puno, software evaluation, Lighthouse

1 Introduction

Web applications add new challenges to developers in the use of Requirements Engineering (RE). As has been the case at other times in the history of software engineering [24].

Websites have evolved over time, making it easier for people to perform a variety of crucial tasks such as selling and buying goods, performing short tasks, controlling smart homes and managing bank accounts. [17] The design of the information architecture of a website is not a simple task, and requires a careful analysis of its objectives and the needs to be satisfied by the different users, the same information may be structured in different ways [24]

There is no doubt that in recent years the tourism sector has experienced continuous growth and diversification to become one of the fastest growing

economic sectors in the world. In today’s digital era, tourism enthusiasts have turned mass media platforms into their main stage to share their experiences, experiences and opinions. Social networks, instant messaging groups, blogs and forums, among others, have become daily channels for the transmission of these experiences to third parties. [27] [33].

Digitalization has transformed the landscape of rural tourism, not only bringing benefits, but also becoming a fundamental instrument for its sustainable and competitive development. Digitalization has allowed the implementation of best practices in the management and promotion of rural destinations, facilitating access to broader and more diverse markets.[12]. In the tourism environment, technology allows tourist destinations to adapt with agility to the demands and preferences of visitors, optimizing both customer satisfaction and operational efficiency. [1].

The annual growth rate of inbound tourism in Puno for the period 1992 - 2015 was 10.7%. The most visited places have been: Taquile Island, Uros Island, national reserve, Amantani Island and the archaeological complex of Silustani. [3]. Digital transformation has had a significant impact on tourism business models, adopting a holistic approach that improves operational efficiency and customer satisfaction [34].

Rural community-based tourism is emerging as a sustainable and viable option for the economic progress of rural communities, especially in areas with a rich cultural heritage and biodiversity such as Puno, Peru. This is why it is now being developed in the Andean region of Latin America as an alternative to conventional tourism, and constitutes a complementary activity to traditional forms of production [2].

Studies on the impact of rural tourism on economic income and its effects on the decision to emigrate received little attention. Most of the works have provided information on promotion, quality of service, demand and supply studies. [2].

Community-based tourism does not only involve air-conditioned environments such as museums or interpretation centers, but also many of the activities such as festivals, concerts, parades, exhibitions, historical scenery tourism, sports tourism, guided tours of the city or visits to monuments. [6]. For this reason, destinations must adapt their offer to the new needs of this emerging customer profile by offering products and services focused on the creation of tourism experiences [11].

One strategy to reduce migration from the countryside to the city has been to explore new economic opportunities, under this context, the idea of promoting rural tourism arises, with the intention that farmers can stay in their places of birth in order to generate their own economy from the production of tourism services [2].

Therefore, tourism, as a complementary activity in the communities, should be conceived to improve the standard of living and quality of life of the inhabitants, generating sustainable growth and local improvement synergies [25].

The implementation of digital platforms for the management of this type of tourism not only increases the accessibility and visibility of these destinations, but also improves the user experience and operational efficiency of local tourism businesses. Therefore, Digital Technologies for

Sustainable Tourism Destinations highlights the importance of adopting emerging technologies to improve the sustainability and operational efficiency of tourism destinations [14].

The importance of creating value from social data in smart tourism destinations, allowing for more effective management and the creation of personalized tourism experiences [5]. The quality of digital marketing initiatives has a direct impact on the image of rural destinations and on tourists' intention to visit them, which in turn contributes to the overall sustainability of the destination [9].

Puno's tourism offer is characterized by its wide variety of destinations. Visitors can explore the city of Puno or venture out to discover the unique Uros Floating Islands, the culturally rich Taquile and Amantani Islands, the picturesque Capachica Peninsula, historic Chucuito and Atuncolla (which in recent years have experienced remarkable progress in infrastructure and accessibility), the charming city of Lampa with the archaeological complex of Pucara, the imposing Tinajani Canyon in the province of Melgar, and the captivating cities of Juli and Pomata with their imposing temples in the province of Chucuito. Finally, the province of Yunguyo offers the impressive archipelago of Wiñaymarca [3].

Digital platforms not only expand the visibility and accessibility of tourism destinations, but also offer users a personalized and enriched experience. In the context of eTourism, technology empowers tourism destinations to adapt with agility to the needs and preferences of visitors, resulting in greater customer satisfaction and operational efficiency [1].

In this sense, this article presents the implementation of a digital platform specifically designed to manage and promote rural tourism in the Puno region. From the point of view of software engineering, one of the main characteristics that a web application must have to be successful is that it must be of high quality [20]. Using modern technologies such as CodeIgniter, which has the administration part, in which some functionalities are already implemented to make the development much more efficient, for the development of the backend and MySQL for database management [18] [7]. Allowing new features to be added without risking the stability and performance of the entire system.

Phillips and Jones (2020) examine the role of social networks in the digital transformation of tourism, highlighting their influence on the promo-

tion and management of tourism destinations [26]. On the other hand Nelson and Roberts (2021) discuss the future trends in tourism, focusing on digital transformation and technological innovation [23].

In addition, it integrates with Google Maps to provide an enriched user experience, allowing visitors to explore destinations through interactive maps and obtain detailed information about each location.

Faced with the digitalization and globalization scenario we are living in, digital platforms for rural tourism management are a viable and necessary alternative. The methodology used in the development of this platform follows an agile approach, specifically the Scrum framework, which allowed an iterative and flexible implementation, adapting to the changing needs of users and project requirements.

2 Methodology

2.1 Design

The main objective of this project is to evaluate the performance of a digital platform for the management of rural tourism in Puno. Therefore, the type of research of the project will be applied, focused on solving specific practical problems related to the management of rural tourism in Puno.

To evaluate the effectiveness and efficiency of the platform, this research is based on a quantitative approach, focusing on the collection and analysis of numerical data to evaluate the effectiveness and efficiency of the platform. Quantitative metrics will provide objective information on system performance, enabling accurate and reliable evaluation.

2.2 System Design

In order to schematize the fundamental procedures of the application, flow charts were created that detail the entire process that the user must follow within the page, providing a clear and organized visual representation.

Figure 1: System Design Flowchart

The system design flowchart graphically represents the procedure that a user must follow to make a reservation on the rural tourism platform. This process is fundamental to the operation of the platform, as it allows users to select tourist destinations and formalize their reservations.

Entering the Home page, the starting point of the process is the user's decision to make a new reservation through the platform, followed by the selection of the Destination, where through a user interface that shows the available tourist destinations with their descriptions and prices, the user navigates through the options and selects the destination he/she wishes to visit.

The next step is to enter the reservation data, where once the destination has been selected, the user must complete the reservation process by providing the required information, such as the

date of the visit, the number of people and any special requirements he/she may have. Next is the Reservation confirmation, which to finalize the process, the user reviews and confirms the reservation. This action records the information in the database and sends a confirmation to the user indicating that the reservation has been successful.

There is also the option to initiate payment, where the process is initiated at the moment the user makes the decision to pay for a previously confirmed reservation. Then the user chooses the payment method he/she wishes to use, and can choose between Yape, credit card or other options available on the platform.

Finally, there is the option to enter payment details, with the chosen payment method, the user enters the necessary details to finalize the transaction. These details may include credit card information or the cell phone number linked to Yape. And finally there is the payment confirmation, which is the last step, the user reviews the payment data entered and confirms the transaction. Upon confirmation, the payment is processed, the information is stored in the system and a payment confirmation is sent to the user.

Data Model

The rural tourism platform data model serves as a basis for understanding the key entities and their interactions. This structure is essential for the organization and effective storage of information in the database.

Figure 2: Data Model

Where in users, data is entered for the creation of accounts on the platform. The mandatory fields to fill out are: user ID, name, email, phone number and password.

In the reservations section, the data is about travel reservations made by users through the platform. The required fields are: reservation identifier, user identifier, destination identifier, reservation date, number of people and reservation status.

In the destinations option, the information is available on the platform, where the fields to be filled in are the destination identification number, destination name, destination description, destination location and destination price.

And finally in payments are data on the reservations made by users through the platform, the required fields are, payment identifier, reservation identifier, payment method used, amount paid, payment status and date of payment.

- Users to Reservations: One-to-many (one user can make multiple bookings).
- Destinations to Reservations: One to many (one destination can have multiple reservations).
- Reservations to Payments: One at a time (each reservation has an associated payment).

2.3 Choice of Technologies

Choosing the right technologies is a critical step in the development of any application, as it determines the robustness, scalability and maintainability of the system. In this document, the technologies selected for the development of the digital platform for rural tourism management in Puno are presented, along with the justifications for their choice.

Coldelgniter was used for the backend, which stands out as a PHP framework for web development due to its compact structure and efficient performance. This was used to develop the internal logic of the application, handle HTTP requests, interact with the database and deliver the views to the user. Specific functionalities to be implemented include user management, reservations, destinations and payments.

Bootstrap was also used because it stands out as a front-end development framework that facilitates the creation of responsive websites, which means

that they adapt perfectly to the screen of the device used, whether it is a desktop computer, a tablet or a cell phone. The use of this tool is to design the user interface of the platform, focusing on creating an attractive and accessible interface for users. Elements such as reservation forms, payment buttons, navigation menus and tourist destination business cards were implemented.

MySQL was used for the database, which stands out as an open source relational database management system due to its reliability, performance and ease of use. This will be used to store and manage platform data, including user, destination, booking and payment information. An optimized database structure was designed to ensure speed and efficiency in information retrieval.

2.4 Evaluation Metrics

The evaluation of the quality of the digital platform for rural tourism management in Puno was based on a series of quantitative metrics designed to measure different aspects of the software. [32] This is an open source automated tool developed by Google that helps to improve the quality of web pages. Lighthouse provides audits in five key areas: performance, accessibility, best practices, SEO and Progressive Web App (PWA) features. Software evaluation using automated tools provides objective and reproducible data, which is essential to efficiently identify areas requiring improvement [15].

Performance is where the platform performance evaluation was performed by Lighthouse, analyzing metrics such as First Contentful Paint (FCP), Speed Index, Time to Interactive (TTI), First Meaningful Paint (FMP) and First CPU Idle. Accessibility: The accessibility of the platform was also evaluated, measuring parameters such as color contrast, the correct application of aria labels, the possibility of keyboard navigation and the inclusion of alternative texts in the images.

Best Practices: The best practices assessment covered HTTPS protocol implementation, JavaScript vulnerability prevention, secure cookie configuration, and optimized loading of critical resources.

SEO: It was used to evaluate the search engine optimization (SEO) of the platform. The key metrics analyzed were the presence of meta descriptions, appropriate title tags, alt attributes on images, readable URLs and the correct implementation of internal and external links.

Progressive Web App (PWA): Lighthouse was also used to evaluate the Progressive Web App (PWA) features of the platform. The existence of a service worker, a manifest.json file, offline responsiveness, mobile compatibility and the possibility of installation as an application were verified. These aspects are crucial to optimize the user experience on mobile devices.

2.5 Results and Discussion

According to Moreno-Izquierdo and Cegarra-Navarro (2021) highlight the challenges and opportunities that the digital era presents for the tourism industry, underlining the need to adapt marketing and management strategies to new technologies [21]. On the other hand Havlinova and Weismann (2022) conducted a systematic review of the literature on smart tourism destinations and digital inclusion, highlighting the importance of integrating digital technologies to improve accessibility and user experience [10].

Also Neal and Remy (2019) examine digital marketing strategies in the tourism sector, identifying the opportunities and challenges faced by companies in implementing these strategies [22]. Finally, Gómez and Hernández (2023) provide an overview of digital tools and technologies for tourism management, presenting the current trends that are transforming the industry. [8].

Lighthouse Performance Comparison Chart

Metrics	Smartphone	Desktop
Performance	100	100
Accessibility	92	92
Recommendations	96	96
SEO	83	83

Table 1: Comparison of Lighthouse results from the homepage home tab for smartphones and desktops

According to Table 1, the PERFORMANCE score is 100 which indicates that on both smartphones and desktop, the page loads extremely fast. This is crucial to provide an optimal user experience and reduce bounce rates. Previous research has shown that loading speed and efficiency are crucial factors for user satisfaction and sustained engagement with the platform.

In terms of ACCESSIBILITY a score of 92 was obtained both on smartphones and desktop, this reflects that the site is highly accessible to users with different abilities. However, there is room for further improvement to provide an

even more accessible experience. Improving these aspects is vital to ensure that the platform is usable by people with diverse abilities, aligning with global accessibility recommendations [28]. The importance of accessibility in web design is underscored by Sigala and Marinidis (2019), who argue that proper accessibility not only complies with regulations, but also expands the potential user base [29].

For BEST PRACTICES a score of 96 was achieved, which reflects that the site follows most of the best practices of web development. This includes safety, load efficiency and the implementation of modern standards. This includes the use of HTTPS, secure cookie management and efficient loading of critical resources, all of which are critical to maintaining system security and efficiency.

On the other hand for SEO a score of 83 was obtained on both smartphones and desktop which shows that the site is well optimized for search engines, but there are specific areas that could be improved to increase visibility in search results. Improving these aspects can significantly increase the platform’s visibility in search engines, attracting more organic traffic [16].

Metrics	Smartphone	Desktop
Performance	43	82
Accessibility	91	91
Recommendations	96	93
SEO	83	83

Table 2: Comparison of Lighthouse results for the “Destinations” tab. on smartphones and desktops

On the other hand for Figure 2 the PERFORMANCE of the destination tab in Puno obtained a score of 82 for desktop devices. This score indicates that, although the site performs reasonably well, there are areas that require optimization to improve loading speed and interactivity. However, a score of 43 was obtained for smartphones, which indicates that the site has significant speed problems on mobile devices. This can be due to several factors such as large images, unoptimized JavaScript code or lack of resource compression.

The platform’s ACCESSIBILITY was evaluated with a score of 91 for smartphones and desktop devices. This high score reflects the company’s commitment to inclusion and accessibility for users with diverse abilities. Items evaluated include color contrast, correct implementation of ARIA labels, and keyboard navigability.

The BEST PRACTICES evaluation yielded a

score of 93, indicating that the platform follows most of the industry standard recommendations for web development. In contrast, a score of 96 was obtained for smartphones, which indicates that adherence to best practices is very high for mobile devices, indicating a good level of security and efficiency.

And finally for SEO the score was 83 for devices such as smartphones and desktop, which is a good indication that the platform is well optimized for search engines. Through the PWA evaluation, it has been determined that the platform has the foundations to provide an optimized user experience on mobile devices. However, it is necessary to continue to review and optimize these features to ensure full and efficient operation in all contexts.

The results of the Lighthouse audits for the “Destinations” tab of the “Virtual Puno” platform show a noticeable difference in performance between smartphones and desktops. While ACCESSIBILITY and SEO are consistent on both, performance on mobile devices is significantly lower, suggesting the need for specific optimizations to improve the experience on these devices. Despite these differences, the platform shows a good level of compliance with best practices and accessibility, which is a positive indicator of its overall quality.

Tan and Hamid (2020) review emerging technologies and their future impact on tourism, stressing the need for technological adoption to maintain competitiveness [31]. As well as Smith and Murphy (2021) who discuss the digital transformation in tourism, focusing on technology adoption and its implications [30].

Johnson and Lee (2019) discuss tourism management in the digital age, highlighting the challenges and strategies needed to cope with technological changes [13]. On the other hand Martin and Williams (2022) explore digital marketing for tourism, identifying current trends and future directions [19]. And authors Clark and Kim (2019) address smart tourism and data analytics, highlighting the opportunities and challenges of integrating these technologies [4].

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